

Relationship Bank's Management Efficiency and Client Firm's Performance: A Case of Pakistan

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Abstract

Firm-bank relationship is a matter of interest as a strong bonding may lead to a better performance of the client firm. The foggy mirror of the fate of such relationships needs more clarification on the said matter. This research investigated the effect of management efficiency of relationship bank on its client firm's performance. The data set consists of the observations for the period from 2006-2016. All the non-financial listed firms on Pakistan Stock Exchange are taken for analysis. We have taken all the common proxies for the firm performance like ROA, ROS, ROE and Tobin's Q and regressed them over bank-specific and firm-specific variables. For management efficiency, two types of measurements are considered, i.e., ME and LME. Our results have reported management efficiency of the relationship bank as a vital factor in explaining the fate of firm-bank relationship and its performance. It is found to be significant and positive for client firm's performance. Further analysis has exposed that if the increased number of firm-bank relationship causes an increase in financial cost as well, then the benefit of maintaining a relationship with a bank (efficient in management) is set off.

Keywords: Firm-bank Relationship, firm performance, Management Efficiency, multi-bank relationship

Introduction

Competition is not a new phenomenon; it remains a matter of concern for the non-financial business firms for decades. The said scenario has become more adverse with the inclusion of innovation and information technology as it results in the competitive environment more complex and demanding for the business firms. A well-recognized remedy for competition in practice is the horizontal and vertical integration of the business in order to achieve un-breakable supplies of needed resources. Among all others, finance and capital is also a very important resource for the firms which has to be managed properly. For the said reason, firms are maintaining relationships with the banks so that they are provided with the required finance as per demand, and the chances of credit rationing are reduced.

Firm-bank relationship is not only important for providing finance to the client firms, but they also build a reputation for the client firms in the market (James, 1987). Campbell (1979) suggested the same by reporting an increase in trust standings and decrease in leakage of information as a result of the firm-bank relationship. Somehow, for some datasets, researchers are still confused about the advantages and disadvantages of such firm-bank relationships. Therefore, the generalizability of a firm-bank relationship's impact on firm performance is still under question. The available literature on the said topic can be classified into three categories, first who believes it is beneficial for the client firm, second who argues about its negative effect on firm performance and third believes such firm-bank relationship have no significant impact. These arguments have their own implications and variables for the studies. In this research we tried to relate the client firm's performance not only with the firm-bank relationship but also include some relationship bank's specific variables who can be decisive for the fate of the firm-bank relationship. Sultan, Javed, Bhutta, and Qing (2016), a prior study on Pakistani market has suggested that the number of firm-bank relationships has a positive and significant impact on client firm's performance. This study is an extension of the prior study as it includes bank-level variables as well to develop a better understanding of the firm-bank relationship phenomenon.

Literature

The foremost research as per knowledge on firm-bank relationship was related to bank loans by James (1987) whereas, the most recent research is established by Sultan, Qing, and Abid (2016) in which researchers analyze a new market (developing market) as most of the prior researchers were based on developed market like U.S.A, Japan, Italy, and others. A variety of ways are there to establish a firm-bank relationship, and a stream of benefits is associated with such kinds of firm-bank relationships such as enriched business standing (Campbell, 1979), remedy against hold-up problem (Bolton & Scharfstein, 1996) & distorted information (Bolton & Freixas, 2000) and increase accessibility to loans with reduction in cost of financing (Bhaumik & Piesse, 2008; Clarke, Cull, & Peria, 2002).

Taking client firm's performance, James (1987) reports that there is a positive relationship between a client firm's stock performance and an announcement of the fresh credit line. Furthermore, James finding contrasts between an arm's length private debt and bank loan by posting a negative effect for private loan whereas a positive impact of bank credit line on client firm's stock performance. This positive behavior in client firm's stock performance is attributed to trust building and additional monitoring by firm-bank relationship.

Another aspect of this firm-bank relationship is that it allows relationship bank/s to gather crucial information about client firms which allows a relationship bank to engineer and offer a non-market tailor made a loan to its client firm/s (Bhattacharya & Chiesa, 1995). In this way, a firm-bank relationship results in shrinkage of asymmetric information and reusability of such information is optimized (Albareto, Benvenuti, Mocetti, Pagnini, & Rossi, 2011; Boot, 2000).

Firm-bank relationship and its importance for client firm/s are unquestionable, but certain indicators are yet to be explored in the light of Khwaja and Mian (2008) as they report the relationship banks have a habit to transfer their risks to their client firms. Therefore, bank's financial health and management efficiency is also an important indicator of the firm-bank relationship's performance. Delis, Kokas, and Ongena (2016) are of the view that in U.S non-financial firms that are poorly performing in the market tends to establish a firm-bank relationship with such a bank having a better standing in the market in terms of financial health and management efficiency and effectiveness.

There is no doubt about the importance of such firm-bank relationship established by client firms as we can find a variety of literature on the said topic but the effect of these relationships is yet to establish. The fate of this relationship is not only based on the firm level factors but also dependent on certain characteristics of the relationship banks as well. Most of the researchers in the past have focused on the firm-level indicators such as firm size, tangibility, leverage, liquidity, growth and age while explaining the mechanism of firm-bank relationship (Angelini, Di Salvo, & Ferri, 1998; Cenni, Monferrà, Salotti, Sangiorgi, & Torluccio, 2015; Chen, Li, & Zhang, 2015; Morck, Nakamura, & Shivdasani, 2000; Thanh & Ha, 2013; Yao & Ouyang, 2007). Extension to the existing research we enhance the model of firm performance in relation to relationship banks by including certain bank-level independent variables like management quality, asset quality, and liquidity.

Research methodology

The research is of empirical nature thus the data set is based on the secondary form of data which has been collected from published annual reports and OSIRIS database. The data set consists of all the listed firms on Pakistan Stock Exchange (PSE) during the period from 2006-2016. The listed firms in PSE are registered under different categories having a grand total of 550. The firms are taken from all the industries in order to generalize the results of the study, but we have excluded the firms which are newly registered and the data for which are electronically unavailable for analysis. This makes our sample to get shorten up to 338 firms almost distributed in every sector. The major sectors include textile 155, sugar 34, chemical 28, cement 20, automobile 21, power generation 18, oil and gas 16 and banking & financial firms 124. For the current study, we have considered only the non-financial firms excluding the banking and financial firms that decrease the number of firms to 404.

Regression analysis is a statistical process for estimating the relationship between variables. It includes many techniques for modeling and analyzing several variables. More specifically, regression analysis helps one understand how the typical value of the dependent variable changes when any one of the independent variables is varied, while the other independent variables are held fixed (Sekaran, 2006). The most simplified form of regression is as follows:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * X_1$$

The major empirical models used in the study are:

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ME_{it} + \beta_2 ME_{it-1} + \beta_3 F_{AGE}_{it} + \beta_4 F_{GROWTH}_{it} + \beta_5 F_{TANG}_{it} + \beta_6 F_{SIZE}_{it} + \beta_7 F_{LIQ}_{it} + \beta_8 NBR_{it} + \beta_9 FC_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \quad (M1)$$

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ME_{it} + \beta_2 ME_{it-1} + \beta_3 F_{AGE}_{it} + \beta_4 F_{GROWTH}_{it} + \beta_5 F_{TANG}_{it} + \beta_6 F_{SIZE}_{it} + \beta_7 F_{LIQ}_{it} + \beta_8 NBR_{it} + \beta_9 MQ_{it-1} * FC_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \quad (M2)$$

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ME_{it} + \beta_2 ME_{it-1} + \beta_3 F_{AGEit} + \beta_4 F_{GROWTHit} + \beta_5 F_{TANGit} + \beta_6 F_{SIZEit} + \beta_7 F_{LIQit} + \beta_8 NBRit + \beta_9 MQit - 1 * FCit + \beta_{10} MQit - 1 * FCit * NBRit + \epsilon_{it}$$

(M3)

$$TQ_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ME_{it} + \beta_2 ME_{it-1} + \beta_3 F_{AGEit} + \beta_4 F_{GROWTHit} + \beta_5 F_{TANGit} + \beta_6 F_{SIZEit} + \beta_7 F_{LIQit} + \beta_8 NBRit + \beta_9 FCit + \epsilon_{it}$$

(M4)

$$TQ_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ME_{it} + \beta_2 ME_{it-1} + \beta_3 F_{AGEit} + \beta_4 F_{GROWTHit} + \beta_5 F_{TANGit} + \beta_6 F_{SIZEit} + \beta_7 F_{LIQit} + \beta_8 NBRit + \beta_9 MQit - 1 * FCit + \epsilon_{it}$$

(M5)

$$TQ_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ME_{it} + \beta_2 ME_{it-1} + \beta_3 F_{AGEit} + \beta_4 F_{GROWTHit} + \beta_5 F_{TANGit} + \beta_6 F_{SIZEit} + \beta_7 F_{LIQit} + \beta_8 NBRit + \beta_9 MQit - 1 * FCit + \beta_{10} MQit - 1 * FCit * NBRit + \epsilon_{it}$$

(M6)

$$ROS_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ME_{it} + \beta_2 ME_{it-1} + \beta_3 F_{AGEit} + \beta_4 F_{GROWTHit} + \beta_5 F_{TANGit} + \beta_6 F_{SIZEit} + \beta_7 F_{LIQit} + \beta_8 NBRit + \beta_9 FCit + \epsilon_{it}$$

(M7)

$$ROS_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ME_{it} + \beta_2 ME_{it-1} + \beta_3 F_{AGEit} + \beta_4 F_{GROWTHit} + \beta_5 F_{TANGit} + \beta_6 F_{SIZEit} + \beta_7 F_{LIQit} + \beta_8 NBRit + \beta_9 MQit - 1 * FCit + \epsilon_{it}$$

(M8)

$$ROS_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ME_{it} + \beta_2 ME_{it-1} + \beta_3 F_{AGEit} + \beta_4 F_{GROWTHit} + \beta_5 F_{TANGit} + \beta_6 F_{SIZEit} + \beta_7 F_{LIQit} + \beta_8 NBRit + \beta_9 MQit - 1 * FCit + \beta_{10} MQit - 1 * FCit * NBRit + \epsilon_{it}$$

(M9)

$$ROE_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ME_{it} + \beta_2 ME_{it-1} + \beta_3 F_{AGEit} + \beta_4 F_{GROWTHit} + \beta_5 F_{TANGit} + \beta_6 F_{SIZEit} + \beta_7 F_{LIQit} + \beta_8 NBRit + \beta_9 FCit + \epsilon_{it}$$

(M10)

$$ROE_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ME_{it} + \beta_2 ME_{it-1} + \beta_3 F_{AGEit} + \beta_4 F_{GROWTHit} + \beta_5 F_{TANGit} + \beta_6 F_{SIZEit} + \beta_7 F_{LIQit} + \beta_8 NBRit + \beta_9 MQit - 1 * FCit + \epsilon_{it}$$

(M11)

$$ROE_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ME_{it} + \beta_2 ME_{it-1} + \beta_3 F_{AGEit} + \beta_4 F_{GROWTHit} + \beta_5 F_{TANGit} + \beta_6 F_{SIZEit} + \beta_7 F_{LIQit} + \beta_8 NBRit + \beta_9 MQit - 1 * FCit + \beta_{10} MQit - 1 * FCit * NBRit + \epsilon_{it}$$

(M12)

Analysis

In order to analyze the effect of management efficiency, we have formulated a three-step model for this research. Theoretical understanding makes us believe that the management efficiency of the relationship has a lag relationship with the future outcomes of the client firms. Therefore, we investigate this understanding with model M1, M4, M7, and M10. The expanded analysis for further stages used the combination terms of management efficiency, financial cost and number of firm-bank relationships. This specification of different models with different combination terms helps us to understand better and elaborate the relationship between the dependent and independent variables of the research.

Table-1 shows the results for our first two performance variables with respect to relationship bank's management efficiency. Model 1 for ROA used management efficiency (ME), the lag of management efficiency (MEL1) as independent variables and another firm-specific and bank-specific variables such as age, growth, tangibility, size; liquidity is presented in the model for controlling purpose. The results for ROA model 1 confirms our theoretical understanding about management efficiency of the relationship bank as for current management efficiency results in relation to client firm's performance has no significant result, but the coefficient has shown a positive effect. Whereas, when we generated a lag variable for the management efficiency of the relationship bank, it shows significant and healthy coefficient (0.0271) at 5% confidence interval.

Results of Management Efficiency in relations to ROA and Tobin's Q

Independent Variable	ROA Model 1	ROA Model 2	ROA Model 3	TQ Model 1	TQ Model 2	TQ Model 3
ME	0.917	0.701	0.328	0.363	0.479	0.661
	0.0013	-0.0052	-0.0128	0.0545	0.0423	0.0257
MEL1	0.031	0.027	0.173	0.064	0.120	0.214
	0.0271**	0.0286**	0.0172	0.1037*	0.0882	0.0704
F_AGE	0.073	0.086	0.054	0.004	0.004	0.003
	-0.8872*	-0.0861*	-0.0941*	-0.6342***	-0.6370***	-0.6428***
F_GROWTH	0.00	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	0.0070***	0.0069***	0.0065***	0.1742***	0.1740***	0.1733***
F_TANG	0.00	0.000	0.000	0.086	0.072	0.058
	-0.1165***	-0.1151***	-0.1241***	-0.2137*	-0.2237*	0.2355*
F_SIZE	0.413	0.413	0.686	0.899	0.793	0.474
	-0.0068	-0.0069	0.0033	0.0047	0.0097	0.0265
F_LIQ	0.00	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	0.0196***	0.0236***	0.0171***	0.0701***	0.0721***	0.0640***
NBR	0.166	0.283		0.285	0.349	
	0.0171	0.0135		0.0589	0.0515	
F_FC	0.00			0.602		
	-0.7772***			-0.301		
LMEFC		0.210	0.000		0.157	0.010
		-0.0298	0.2026***		0.1478	0.4404*
LMEFCNBR			0.000			0.034
			-0.2100***			-0.2601**
Year effect	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
N	1449	1449	1449	1449	1449	1449
R2	0.1574	0.1207	0.1907	0.3390	0.3241	0.3333

*** Significant at 1% Level

** Significant at 5% Level

*Significant at 10% Level

These results make us believe that the management efficiency of the relationship bank has significantly positive and lag relationship with its client firm's performance. Model 2 for ROA as a dependent variable has used the same specification of the other variables except for the introduction of a combination term of management efficiency lag and financial cost of the firm. The results for the new term has shown a negative relationship with the client firm performance which depicts that the firm will have a negative impact on its performance. But unfortunately, these results are not significant. ROA Model 3 has used a new combination term of Lag ME, financial cost and number of firm-bank relationships. This new variable has shown impressive results with a coefficient of -0.21 that is significant at 1%. The results explain that the firm maintaining more number of bank relationships will bear more financial charges which may result in setting off the benefit of efficient management of relationship bank.

The results for TQ, as it is market performance measurement of the client firm, has shown the same results for management efficiency of the relationship bank. Management efficiency (ME), when it is used for the current year performance comparison shown positive but insignificant results which is again consistent with our theoretical understanding. Whereas, while regressing the empirical model for analyzing the lag relationship, we found positive and significant results. The firm-specific control variables have shown the same results as expected and theoretically proven for all the models for TQ. Using the same specification as ROA, we have introduced two combination terms in model 2 and model 3 for TQ. The combination term has confirmed our results for market performance proxy as well that the bank

management efficiency has a positive impact on the client firm's performance unless the financial cost of the firm is increased with the increase in a number of firm-bank relationships established by a firm. In such case, the positive impact of relationship bank's management efficiency is set off by the negative impact of an increase in financial cost with an increase in firm-bank relationships. The results as shown in table-1 express our significant results with a coefficient of -0.2501. We have further strengthened our analysis by including other two frequently used performance variables in the literature (ROS and ROE). Table-2 depicts the results of the regression with ROS and ROE for all the three model specification same as used earlier. Results for ROS were also found to significant only when we used management efficiency of the relationship bank in lag. Moreover, the model 3 for ROA has revealed the same for combination term (LMEFCNBR). Analysis for ROE has the same conclusions except for the combination terms. The results were found again negative but unfortunately with no significance.

Results of Management Efficiency in relations to ROS and ROE

Independent Variable	ROS Model 1	ROS Model 2	ROS Model 3	ROE Model 1	ROE Model 2	ROE Model 3
ME	0.888	0.690	0.698	0.314	0.313	0.319
	-0.0085	-0.0240	-0.0230	-0.0874	-0.0875	-0.0849
MEL1	0.026	0.064	0.133	0.012	0.004	0.005
	0.1264**	0.1072*	0.0871	0.2030	0.0236***	0.2300***
F_AGE	0.677	0.847	0.869	0.125	0.137	0.125
	-0.01378	-0.0063	-0.0053	-0.4880	-0.4737	-0.4882
F_GROWTH	0.074	0.052	0.061	0.000	0.000	0.000
	0.0121*	0.0131*	0.0126*	-0.0699***	-0.0698***	-0.0699***
F_TANG	0.065	0.055	0.041	0.153	0.194	0.179
	-0.1462*	-0.1517*	-0.1602**	-0.2574	-0.2346	-0.2428
F_SIZE	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.225	0.165	0.192
	0.0603***	0.0601***	0.0553***	-0.0655	-0.0752	-0.0703
F_LIQ	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.590	0.310	0.500
	0.0579***	0.0632***	0.0475***	0.0116	0.0214	0.0147
NBR	0.134	0.075		0.644	0.655	
	-0.0557	-0.0660*		-0.0369	-0.0357	
F_FC	0.243			0.014		
	-0.5856			-2.0549		
LMEFC		0.081	0.000		0.015	0.572
		0.1659*	0.5855***		-0.3697	-0.1396
LMEFCNBR			0.000			0.231
			-0.3792***			-0.2138
Year	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
N	1449	1449	1449	1449	1449	1449
R2	0.1143	0.1285	0.1314	0.0058	0.0052	0.0059

*** Significant at 1% Level

** Significant at 5% Level

*Significant at 10% Level

Findings and conclusions

Horizontal and vertical integration is no more a surprise in this competitive world. To cope with the current competition, firms are inclined towards maintaining a close bonding with the banking companies as these are the only option for meeting the financial needs of the firms. Firms establish bank relationships in different ways, but the most frequent and widely approach is borrower and lender relationship. Certain benefits and objective are associated with such firm-bank relationships maintained by firms. These relationships not only provide a guarantee of timely financing but also have an impact on the client firm's repute and business standings in the overall market.

These relationships have a lot to do with the client firm's performance (Sultan, Qing, et al., 2016). A good firm-bank relationship has a positive impact on client firm's performance (Delis et al., 2016). We have investigated this issue in relation to management efficiency of the relationship bank. The result suggested that the relationship bank's management efficiency influence the client firm's performance in a positive manner. The justification lies in the argument given by Delis et al. (2016) that the relationship with the healthier bank has a positive impact on client firm's performance. An efficient management practices by relationship bank will lead to better evaluation and monitoring of credit and eventually results in a better performance of client firms. Our further investigation makes us understand that this is a lag relationship so a relationship bank that has efficient management in the past year will have a positive impact on the performance of patron firm in the consequent year. The results further explain that if the number of firm-bank relationships is increased with the condition that the financial cost of the client firm is also increased then this management efficiency of

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